

STUDY ON PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' IN WRITING ENGLISH WITHOUT ERRORS

Mrs. Sameera K. K

*Author, Part time Research Scholar, Vels Institute of Science, Technology & Advanced Studies,
Pallavaram, Chennai- 600117.*

Dr. K. Sheeba

*C-Author, Associate Professor in Education, Vels Institute of Science, technology & Advanced
Studies, Pallavaram, Chennai- 600117. Email: sheebakarpagam.k@gmail.com*

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Abstract

The English spelling system is complex and cannot be considered simple or clear for novice learners to comprehend. Orthographic errors can distort the intended message of a written work, rendering it challenging to understand. The sub-skill of spelling is crucial in the acquisition of any language. This study employs an experimental design. From the governmental institution, approximately thirty students from the fifth-grade kids were recruited for the study from the state of Kerala. Out of thirty pupils, fifteen were designated as the control group, while the remaining fifteen comprised the experimental group, which received treatment for ten days. The experimental group received coaching for 10 days focused on writing English words accurately, addressing errors such as omission, substitution, addition, and transposition. The pre-test and post-test have been administered to both the control and experimental groups. The study's findings indicated that pupils who received experimental treatment had more improvement in writing English words accurately. Therefore, it is determined that the treatment is effective. Orthography is essential for language acquisition, particularly for literacy competencies in reading and writing. The conclusion emphasized that boosting spelling is crucial for academic achievement, and each learner must assume responsibility for developing their spelling abilities and integrating them across all skills and sub-skills.

Keywords: Omission, Substitution, Addition, Transposition, Experimental and Control group

INTRODUCTION

Spelling is regarded as one of the most important aspects of language because every piece of writing relies exclusively on spelling skills. Spelling is intimately related to reading and writing

abilities (Hammond, 2001). According to Snow (1999), spelling is the process of writing down or labeling the individual letters that comprise a word. Learning to spell allows children to use words correctly and express themselves in writing, which helps primary school students develop their reading skills. Spelling is more difficult than reading. Typically, people cannot correctly spell words they are unfamiliar with. Learning a language requires spelling and phonics.

Spelling in English is complicated, and it cannot be stated that the spelling system is simple or easy for a beginner to grasp. The majority of pupils struggle with English written form (spelling) since it must represent their views and thoughts, as well as the negative consequences of failing to utilize it correctly and acquire language abilities. As a result, proper spelling is considered essential for written materials. Spelling errors can change the meaning of a piece of text, making it harder to understand. As a result, precise spelling is critical for conveying the exact meaning of the article.

The four major forms of errors in spelling are as follows:

- **Omission:** The error is the omission of a single letter, e.g., happening for occurring.
- **Insertion:** The error is the insertion of a single letter, such as off for of.
- **Substitution:** The error involves replacing a single letter with another, such as definate for definite.
- **Transposition:** The error involves misordering two neighbouring characters, such as lable for label. (Occasionally, a single letter may have been misplaced in more than one position in a word, such as litgh for light; this should still be considered a transposition.)

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The ability to interpret letter patterns as words, which eventually results in word recognition, is known as orthographic spelling skills. The goal of Sanaria and Atta's (2025) study is to evaluate the value of offering extra resources in elementary schools to help students with their orthographic spelling. To address the research subject, the researchers employed a quantitative, quasi-experimental methodology. 42 pupils from a private elementary school in Sulaymaniyah, Iraq, made up the study's sample. Data analysis was done using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The data was analyzed using the independent samples t-test. Data was collected utilizing pre-test and post-test findings from the experimental and control groups, with a particular emphasis on sixth grade. According to the study's findings, students from the experimental group significantly improved their spelling abilities when given extra materials to help them learn orthographic spelling in the English language. Teachers,

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educators, or legislators may find the findings useful in incorporating orthographic spelling exercises into primary school English language curricula.

Given the significance of studying English for both education and employment, students must master the four language skills in order to use the language efficiently. Spelling is seen as essential for written texts and is a crucial component of writing proficiency. Spelling errors can alter the true meaning of a piece of writing, making it harder to interpret. When teaching English as a second language in India, spelling instruction is usually neglected. The study conducted by Wahaj Unnisa Warda, Abdul Awal Dinjata, and Mohammad Rezaul Karim (2023) aims to ascertain the gaps and problems Indian primary school pupils have when spelling English words, as well as their present level of spelling ability. A type of descriptive survey was the research methodology employed for this study. The study's sample consisted of kids who attended the primary school run by the Jalpaiguri Municipal Corporation in West Bengal, India. Ogive and normal probability curves were developed to examine the frequency distribution of the English Diagnostic Test findings. The sample's and its subsamples' central tendencies were examined. The study found that although there is no statistically significant difference in spelling proficiency between elementary school students based on gender or the medium of instruction they receive, there are significant differences depending on whether they attend government or non-government schools.

In the 2015 study, Dada and Esther evaluated students' essay writing faults, their origins, the impact these errors had on their performance, and potential remedial techniques. For the study, a survey-type descriptive research design was used. All of the secondary schools in Ondo State's Akure South Local Government Area made up the population. 175 pupils and instructors were randomly chosen from five secondary schools in the surrounding area (30 students and 5 teachers each school) to make up the sample. Two tools were employed to gather the data. Essays written by students were used as a corpus for analysis in order to find patterns in spelling mistakes, and teachers were given a self-made and validated questionnaire to answer questions about the reasons behind errors, their impact, and possible correction techniques. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages were used to analyze the acquired data. The findings indicated that among other spelling mistakes, pupils' compositions frequently had omissions, additions, and reduplications of letters. There aren't many books in school libraries that focus on spelling mistakes, and students typically don't take the time to proofread their work after writing. These are some of the reasons why mistakes are made.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Improving one's spelling is a crucial component of learning any language. Students need to grasp and be proficient in the basics of spelling if they want to succeed in English Language and all subjects (since English is the language of instruction). The capacity to write, and by extension, spell, is an essential skill in any and all contexts. It should be emphasized that in academic settings, it is essential to recognize the correct spelling of terms. According to Graham (2012), a strong foundation for education is provided by an improved command of spelling. Many elementary school pupils have no trouble expressing themselves orally but have difficulty putting their thoughts into writing for reasons unrelated to poor spelling or grammar (Kamhi, 2000). Teaching children good spelling practices and how to avoid spelling mistakes at a young age improves their capacity to receive, recall, and communicate information (Bernhardt, 2005).

Spelling correctly helps authors present their ideas and views in a clear and concise way that readers can understand. Proper spelling is essential for competent writers. Having sufficient material and the suitable forms of English words that impact writing is essential for everyone who wishes to communicate through writing. Writing relies on accurate spelling, which is a complex ability in and of itself. A well-spelled word helps convey meaning in written form and is thus expected of by society. Writing relies on accurate spelling, which is a complex ability in and of itself. A well-spelled word helps convey meaning in written form and is thus expected of by society. Since it lays the framework for successful communication, reading, and cognitive development, spelling in elementary school has a significant influence on a child's academic and personal growth. Therefore, this research is vitally necessary right now for the people who will live in our nation tomorrow.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs an experimental design. Approximately thirty students from the fifth-grade pupils were selected for the study from a government institution in the state of Kerala. Of the thirty pupils, fifteen were designated as the control group, while the remaining fifteen constituted the experimental group, which received treatment for ten days. The treatment addresses the errors made in writing English words. The faults of omission, substitution, addition, and transposition were elucidated and practiced extensively throughout the course. The pre-test and post-test were administered, and SPSS was utilized to analyze the scores. Following ten days of therapy, students from both the experimental and control groups were administered a post-test in spelling.

RESEARCH QUESTION

1. Is there is any significant mean difference between the Control and Experimental group in the pre-test score in the types of error of the upper primary students?
2. Is there is any significant mean difference between the Control and Experimental group in the pre-test score in the types of error of the upper primary students?
3. Is there is any significant mean difference of control group students between pre-test and post-test of students with managing the spelling error in English Language?
4. Is there is any significant mean difference of control group students between post-test and post-test of students with managing the spelling error in English Language?

ANSWERS TO THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Question - 1

Significance mean difference between the Control and Experimental group in the Pre-test score in the types of error of the upper primary students

Types of Error in Writing skill - Spelling	Group	Mean	Standard Deviation	t value	Level of Significance
Omission	Control	2.46	3.13	1.126	P>0.005 NS
	Experimental	2.8	4.16		
Substitution	Control	2.66	3.34	0.614	P>0.005 NS
	Experimental	2.06	4.31		
Addition	Control	0.93	2.82	1.213	P>0.005 NS
	Experimental	1.1	4.06		
Transposition	Control	0.26	3.36	1.658	P>0.005 NS
	Experimental	1.76	2.87		

Note: NS – Not Significant

It is observed from the above table that there is no difference between the control and experimental group in their type of errors like omission, substitution, addition and transposition in the pre-test.

Question - 2

Significance mean difference between the Control and Experimental group in the Post test score in the types of error of the upper primary students

Types of Error in Writing skill - Spelling	Group	Mean	Standard Deviation	t value	Level of Significance
Omission	Control	2.46	3.02	2.136	P<0.001**
	Experimental	4.8	5.16		
Substitution	Control	2.66	3.52	4.615	P<0.001**
	Experimental	5.06	4.01		
Addition	Control	0.93	2.82	4.618	P<0.001**
	Experimental	5.1	4.06		
Transposition	Control	0.26	3.36	5.858	P<0.001**
	Experimental	5.76	2.87		

** Significant at 0.01 level

It is observed from the above table that there is significant mean difference between the control and experimental group at one percent level. It is inferred that after treatment the experimental group have well improved by coping with errors like omission, substitution, addition and transposition in the post-test.

Question - 3

Mean difference of control group students between pre-test and post-test of students with managing the spelling error in English Language

Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t value	P value
Pre-test	30	09.23	3.231	1.321	P>0.005 NS
Post-test	30	10.34	.2.892		

Note: NS – Not Significant

It is observed from the above table that there is no difference between the pre-test and post-test of students with managing the spelling error in English Language

Question - 4

Mean difference of Experimental group students between pre-test and post-test of students with managing the spelling error in English Language

Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t value	P value
Pre-test	30	9.43	4.541		
Post-test	30	18.34	3.142	8.321	P<0.001**

** Significant at 0.01 level

It is observed from the above table that there is significant mean difference between the pre-test and post-test of students with managing the spelling error in English Language for the experimental group. It is also observed that the significant mean difference is there for one percent level.

CONCLUSION

It is demonstrated in the study that primary pupils can write in English without making mistakes if they receive the right guidance or instruction. Writing is a vital part of human communication, and writing correctly is of the highest significance. Spelling is important when learning a language, especially when it comes to writing and reading. It was determined that each student should take responsibility for increasing their spelling abilities and applying them to all other skills and sub-skills since spelling is crucial for academic achievement.

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